

European Cloud for Heritage Open Science

D1.3 Quality and Risk Management Plan

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Horizon Innovation action

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Executive Summary

The QRMP establishes a robust framework for ensuring high-quality project outcomes and proactive risk management. Key components include:

1. Quality Management Strategy:

- Defined roles and responsibilities within the consortium,
- Quality control measures such as regular progress reporting, milestone tracking, and stakeholder engagement,
- KPIs to monitor achievements across work packages and deliverables.

2. Risk Management Strategy

- Identification of potential risks (scientific, technical, financial, and operational) and mitigation plans,
- Regular risk monitoring and reporting mechanisms, with escalations to governance bodies when necessary,
- Clear assignment of risk ownership to specific roles within the project.

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List of abbreviations

Abb.	
DMP	Data Management Plan
EITF	ECHOES Integration Task Force
ECCCH	European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage
EB	Executive Board
GA	General Assembly
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HDT	Heritage Digital Twin
PAB	Policy Advisory Board
QRMP	Quality and Risk Management Plan
ScS	Scientific Committee
SEP	Single Entry Point
SOs	Specific objectives
StaC	Stakeholders Council
SC	Steering Committee
TAC	Technical Assessment Committee
VAs	Vertical Applications
WP	Work Packages

Introduction

This document serves as the Quality and Risk Management Plan (QRMP) for the ECHOES project, formally titled European Cloud for Heritage OpEn Science. The QRMP outlines the strategies, processes, and tools that will guide the consortium in delivering high-quality outputs while effectively identifying, assessing, and mitigating risks throughout the project lifecycle. It ensures alignment with Horizon Europe standards, including compliance with ethical guidelines, data management protocols, and Open Science principles.

The scope of this document encompasses all activities, deliverables, and objectives described in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement, particularly those contributing to the development of the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH). As an interdisciplinary initiative, ECHOES bridges the fields of cultural heritage, digital humanities, and advanced computational science to empower stakeholders with state-of-the-art tools and resources.

ECHOES aims to establish the ECCCH as a transformative platform that enables heritage professionals and researchers to access data, collaborate on analyses, and co-create knowledge. This digital environment will integrate advanced technologies such as Digital Twins and Artificial Intelligence, fostering new insights into both tangible and intangible cultural heritage.

The project adopts a holistic and inclusive approach, promoting Open Science, Open Access, and Open Source principles to ensure democratized access to knowledge and tools. The ultimate vision is to deliver “the heritage of tomorrow,” semantically rich and collaboratively produced, by the end of the project in Month 60.

Key goals of the project include:

1. The design and implementation of the ECCCH platform.
2. The integration of fragmented communities in cultural heritage around Digital Commons.
3. The delivery of a sustainable governance model for the ECCCH platform, anchored in inclusivity and transparency.

The consortium includes 26 beneficiaries, 16 affiliated entities and 9 associated partner entities across Europe, led by the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS) as the coordinator. With a budget of €23,970,598, ECHOES is structured into clearly defined Work Packages (WPs), each with measurable milestones and deliverables.

This QRMP is organized into two sections:

1. Quality Management Strategy
 - 1.1 Quality Procedures
 - a. Roles and responsibilities
 - b. Quality control measures
 - c. Communication plan
 - d. Document control and archiving
 - 1.2 KPIs
2. Risk Management Strategy
 - 2.1 Risk Identification and Mitigation Plan
 - 2.2 Risk Monitoring and Reporting
 - 2.3 Risk Owner Assignment

By adhering to this framework, the project ensures that all outputs are delivered on time and at the highest quality, in compliance with the Grant Agreement and Horizon Europe guidelines.

This plan is intended as a living document, subject to updates based on project progress, stakeholder feedback, and emerging challenges. By adhering to the QRMP, the ECHOES consortium commits to delivering on its objectives with excellence, transparency, and accountability, ensuring the success and long-term impact of the project.

1. Quality Management Strategy

The primary objective of the Quality Management Strategy is to ensure the delivery of high-quality outputs, compliant with Horizon Europe requirements, including ethical standards, sustainability goals, and Open Science principles. This guarantees that the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) meets the needs of stakeholders and achieves the project's strategic goals.

1.1 Quality Procedures

This section outlines the various roles and responsibilities of the key bodies and individuals within the consortium, detailing their specific functions, reporting structures, and areas of oversight in relation to the project's coordination, management, and execution.

1.1.1 Roles and Responsibilities

Roles	Responsibilities	Member(s)
Coordination Team		
Coordinator	<p>The intermediary between the Parties and the European Commission.</p> <p>Chairs all the meetings of the GA and of the Steering Committee;</p> <p>Oversees the technical implementation and management;</p> <p>Provides, upon request, the Parties with official copies or originals of documents when such copies or originals are necessary for the Parties to present claims;</p> <p>Collects information for the termination report in case of termination of a Party's participation.</p> <p>Reports to the SC, the GA and the EC.</p>	Xavier RODIER (CNRS)
European Project Manager	<p>Oversees the coordination and administrative management of the project at the European level.</p> <p>Ensures compliance with European Commission regulations;</p> <p>Manages the budget, timeline and progress reports;</p> <p>Facilitates communication among international partners.</p> <p>(WP1)</p>	Louise GADOIN (CNRS)
Scientific Project Manager	<p>Focuses on the scientific (cultural heritage community) and research aspects of the project.</p>	Mailane SAMPAIO (CNRS)

	<p>Coordinates research activities, ensures the scientific objectives are met, supports researchers, and integrates scientific outputs into the project's overall goals.</p> <p>(WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5)</p>	
Digital Project Manager	<p>Focuses on the digital and research aspects of the project.</p> <p>Oversees the development and implementation of digital aspects, ensures proper data management and interoperability, and supports technical innovation.</p> <p>(WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9)</p>	Areti DAMALA (CNRS)
Legal Officer	<p>Handles legal and compliance aspects of the project.</p> <p>Ensures adherence to legal frameworks (e.g., intellectual property rights, GDPR), drafts contracts, and advises the consortium on regulatory issues.</p> <p>WP10: identification and implementation of the Cloud's fundamental ethical principles, research on and design of the Cloud's governance structure, research on the most appropriate legal entity to establish for the Cloud + implementation of said legal entity.</p> <p>Reports to the Coordinator.</p> <p>(WP10, W11, WP12)</p>	Léna CZECH (CNRS)
Consortium bodies		
Executive Board (EB)	<p>Operational body.</p> <p>Assists and facilitate the work of the Coordinator in the execution of the General Assembly decisions;</p>	<p>Chair :</p> <p>Emanuel DEMETRESCU (CNR);</p>

	<p>Assists in the preparation of the Steering Committee and other Consortium Bodies meetings.</p> <p>Ensures the political management of the project by defining the strategic orientations and guiding its implementation in line with overall objectives.</p> <p>Reports to the Coordinator.</p>	<p>Members :</p> <p>Marie GAILLE (CNRS);</p> <p>Lionel MAUREL (CNRS);</p> <p>Philippe DILLMAN (CNRS)</p> <p>Xavier RODIER (CNRS);</p> <p>Dimitris KOTZINOS (CNRS);</p> <p>Isabelle PALLOT-FROSSARD (FSP);</p> <p>Rémi PETICOL (FSP);</p> <p>Emmanuel POIRAULT (FSP);</p> <p>Alexandre CAUSSE (FSP);</p> <p>Vania VIRGILI (CNR);</p> <p>Paolo CIGNONI (CNR);</p> <p>Simone BERTO (CNR)</p>
Steering Committee (SC)	<p>Supervisory body for the execution of the Project.</p> <p>Prepares the meetings, propose decisions and prepare the agenda of the General Assembly;</p> <p>Ensures proper execution and implementation of the decisions of the General Assembly;</p> <p>Pursues a consensus among the Parties;</p>	<p>Chair:</p> <p>Coordinator;</p> <p>Pillar coordinators :</p> <p>Isabelle PALLOT-FROSSARD (Community Pillar);</p> <p>Dimitrios KOTZINOS (Knowledge Pillar);</p>

	<p>Assesses deliverables and milestones, ensures they are in line with the scheduled work plan and prepares the periodic reporting for the work packages together with the Coordinator.</p> <p>Reports to the General Assembly</p>	<p>Paolo CIGNONI (Innovation Pillar); Xavier RODIER (Sustainability Pillar).</p> <p>WP leaders (see the list below); The EB Chairperson is a permanent observer.</p>
General Assembly (GA)	<p>Highest decision-making body.</p> <p>Responsible to decide on:</p> <p>Finances and intellectual property rights; Evolution of the consortium (e.g. partners entering/ leaving the consortium); Breach, defaulting party status and litigation; Appointments of the Scientific Committee Members and Technical Assessment Council Members.</p> <p>Final decision-making body.</p>	<p>Chair:</p> <p>Coordinator;</p> <p>One representative by Beneficiary (List available on the Consortium Agreement, Annex 6, p. 99); ECCCH project leaders are permanent observers; Associated Partners are permanent observers.</p>
WP Leaders	<p>Coordinate the completion of activities for the tasks in the relevant Work package.</p>	<p>WP1: Xavier RODIER WP2: Franco NICCOLUCCI WP3: Sally CHAMBERS WP4: Rémi PETITCOL WP5: Ad POLLE</p>

		<p>WP6: Aleksandra NOWAK</p> <p>WP7: Sorin HERMON</p> <p>WP8: Paolo CIGNONI</p> <p>WP9: Carlos ANDUJAR</p> <p>WP10: Philippe VENDRIX</p> <p>WP11: Vania VIRGILI</p> <p>WP12: Dimitrios KOTZINOS</p>
ECHOES Integration Task Force (EITF)	<p>In charge of the integration strategy, the EITF will focus on WP Interactions, decision-making through formal governance, and the process of implementing requirements</p> <p>Develops the ECHOES Integration Roadmap: plans and monitors the selection and integration of datasets, tools and workflows into the ECHOES Platform;</p> <p>Provides a basis for developing the Collaborative Research Scenarios that will focus on re-using resources;</p> <p>Undertakes user testing as part of the continuous assessment of ECHOES tools and services.</p>	<p>Coordinators:</p> <p>Dimitris KOTZINOS (WP1) (CNRS-CYU)</p> <p>Sally CHAMBERS (DARIAH)</p> <p>Matej DURCO with Johan OOMEN (NISV) for Cascading Grants</p> <p>The EITF consists of: ECHOES Work Package Leaders, plus other experts as required:</p> <p>WP1 (CNRS) - Xavier RODIER, Mailane MESSIAS-SAMPAIO, Areti DAMALA, Louise GADOIN</p> <p>WP4 (FSP) - Rémi PETITCOL</p>

WP5 (Europeana) - Julia FALLON/Ad POLLE

WP6 (PSNC) - Aleksandra NOWAK

WP7 (CYI) - Sorin HERMON

WP8 (CNR) - Paolo CIGNONI

WP9 (UPC) - Carlos ANDUJAR

Representatives of the Virtual Applications

VA1: Collaborative Conservation-Restoration Platform (Lead: CNR): Marco CALLIERI

VA2: Virtual Transcription Laboratory (Lead: DARIAH): Anne BAILLOT

VA3: Collection Ingestion Tool (Lead: ETT-META): Sam MINELLI

Representatives from current and future ECCCH-funded projects

AUTOMATA (Holly WRIGHT University of York)

TEXTaiLES (George IOANNAKIS, Athena Research Center)

		HERITALISE (Mikel BORRAS, IDP Ingerieria y Arquitectura Iberia SL)
Independent and External Board of the consortium		
Policy Advisory Board (PAB)	Ensures coherence at the policy level between all ECCCH-related activities; Provides recommendations on strategic decisions related to governance and sustainability of the Cloud within its ecosystem.	Manuel CASTIÑEIRAS GONZALEZ (ES) Chris DE LOOF (BE) David DE ROURE (UK) David FIALA (FR) Pascal LIEVAUX (FR) Paul KELLER (NE) Marina SOLOMIDOU-IERONYMIDOU (CY) Eva STENSKÖLD (SE) Elena THEODOULOU-CHARALAMBOUS (CY) Brigitte VEZINA (NE) Ben WAGNER (NE) Katarzyna WALETKO (PL)
Scientific Committee (ScS)	Provide expert advice not only on activities carried out within ECHOES but also on activities performed in other ECCCH-funded projects once they are integrated into the horizontal infrastructure.	Pere BRUNET (ES) Livio DE LUCA (FR)

		<p>Paola DERUDAS (SE)</p> <p>Diane DUSSEAU (FR)</p> <p>Eero HYVÖNEN (FI)</p> <p>Adeline JOFFRES (FR)</p> <p>Peter PLASSMEYER (DE)</p> <p>Martjn PRONK (NE)</p> <p>Antonino ROTOLO (NE)</p> <p>Roberto SCOPIGNO (IT)</p> <p>Matija STRLIC (SI)</p> <p>Melissa TERRAS (UK)</p> <p>Jean François TRUBERT (FR)</p>
Technical Assessment Committee (TAC)	<p>It will assess the Cloud's structure and the evolving components, tools and services. Once established, it will be linked to the legal entity.</p> <p>Provides expert advice on the technical activities carried out within ECHOES.</p>	<p>It is currently composed of 8 experts from the computer sciences domain and from different sectors of CH.</p> <p>CANDELO Gustavo (ES)</p> <p>GUELTON Rémi (FR)</p> <p>JONES Bob (CH)</p> <p>LESJAK Dejan (SI)</p> <p>LEVERS Andrew (UK)</p>

		<p>NEGRI Antonella (IT)</p> <p>SZPROT Jakub (PO)</p> <p>VAN WEZEL Jos (DE)</p>
Stakeholders Council (StaC)	<p>It will bring together other ECCCH-funded projects and Representatives from European initiatives related to CH.</p> <p>Advises the General Assembly.</p>	<p>Final list expected by Autumn 2025:</p> <p>Gabriele GATTIGLIA (AUTOMATA);</p> <p>Georgios IOANNAKIS (TEXTaiLES);</p> <p>Mikel BORRAS (HERITALISE);</p> <p>Future representatives of ECCCH-funded projects;</p> <p>Representatives from other European initiatives related to CH.</p>

Table 1: Roles and responsibilities

1.1.2 Quality Control Procedures

Quarterly Reports by WP Leaders

WP leaders must submit detailed progress reports every three months, including the planned progress and the actual progress in the mentioned period. If there is a reason for difference or major risks and problems encountered, they must declare it. In addition, the WP leader must present the planned activities for the following three months.

Quarterly Reports by Beneficiaries

Beneficiaries must submit progress reports every three months, including updates about their activities and the work of their Affiliated Entities. They must highlight the contributions made in each Work Package they are involved in and include the quantity of Person-Months engaged during the period.

Quarterly meetings by the Steering Committee

The Work Package leaders, the Pillar Coordinators and the Chair of the Executive Board shall supervise the progress of the project and propose further actions. The purpose of the meeting is to discuss the most relevant topics such as monitoring compliance with milestones and deliverables, the progress of tasks and sub-tasks by WP, and internal and external events.

Monthly follow-up by the Executive Board

The Executive Board, composed of the coordinating institution and the two co-leading institutions, meets once a month to review the project's progress in line with the strategic directions defined by the EB.

Annual Meetings

One general meeting per year of the project will be held with all the partners to review project progress, address cross-WP challenges, and ensure alignment across teams. These meetings will include presentations of WPs' progress, updates on risks, and feedback from stakeholders.

Additionally, the meetings of the Policy Advisory Board, the Scientific Committee, the Technical Assessment Committee and the Stakeholders Council will be convened in the same place and location, after this meeting. The goal is that the members of the independent boards can follow the on-site discussions and be updated on ECHOES's latest achievements and activities carried out during the next year.

The location of the annual meeting will rotate geographically to encourage the participation of stakeholders from different parts of the EU and the engagement with local heritage institutions and policymakers during the public event.

General Assembly

With a representative of each partner, including affiliated entities and associated partners, the role of the General Assembly is to set out decisions to ensure that the activities carried out are compatible with the project described. Except for the first General Assembly that will be held online, all future General Assemblies will be organized jointly with the Annual meetings. Decisive matters may be presented by email as well, according to Section 6.3.1.3 of the Consortium Agreement. The goal is to have an agile procedure while securing the right of every partner to vote and have a voice.

Periodic Reports to the European Commission

Technical and financial reports must be submitted by the Coordinator at the end of each reporting period, as required by Article 21 of the Grant Agreement:

- RP1 (Months 1–24): Due 60 days after Month 24.
- RP2 (Months 25–48): Due 60 days after Month 48.
- RP3 (Months 49–60): Final report due 60 days after project completion.

Deliverables

The internal review process for deliverables will involve a two-tier validation system: one at the WP level and another at the coordinator level. On the WP level, the WP leader oversees the development of the Deliverable under a task or sub-task. The lead beneficiary of the Deliverable is identified on the list of Deliverables available on page 45 of the Grant Agreement. The WP leader must appoint the lead author(s) of the Deliverable and inform the Coordinator up to one month before the deadline.

The Pillar Coordinators conduct the internal review process and must assign one or more collaborators for proofreading. The project manager will send a reminder to the lead author and the WP leader one month before the deliverable submission.

The process for finalizing the deliverable is as follows:

- Four weeks before the deadline: the lead author has one week to complete the final draft of the Deliverable and share with the Coordinator, Pillar Coordinators and Project Manager.
- Three weeks before the deadline: one-week period dedicated to the internal review of the deliverable.
- Two weeks before the deadline: The lead authors must implement the contributions from the reviewers to the final text.
- One week before the deadline: final editing will be done.
- On the last day: the deliverable will be uploaded to the platform.

Responsible	<i>Lead author(s)</i>	<i>Reviewer(s)</i>	<i>Lead author(s)</i>	<i>Coordinator and author</i>	<i>Coordinator</i>
Production timeline	<i>Four weeks before</i>	<i>Three weeks before</i>	<i>Two weeks before</i>	<i>One week before</i>	<i>Deadline</i>
Task	<u>Final draft provided</u>	<u>Internal review</u>	<u>Implementation of requested changes</u>	<u>Revision/Final editing (CO)</u>	<u>Upload</u>
	Final version submitted by the lead author	Check the consistency with the project plans and give feedback and/or approval.	Check the consistency with the project plans and give feedback and/or approval.	Final formatting and language check	Upload on the Funders & Tenders Portal

Table 2: Deliverable timeline

All deliverables listed in the Grant Agreement must undergo internal review before being submitted to the granting authority via the EU Funding and Tenders Portal.

In case of possible delay of Deliverable, the lead author shall inform the Coordinator by email with a detailed explanation of the reason and the estimated future date. This should be done at least before the start day of the internal process review, four weeks before the deadline. The Coordinator will contact the Project Officer to notify the delay.

1.2 Internal communication plan

Effective communication is crucial for the success of the ECHOES project, ensuring seamless coordination among all partners and work packages. This communication plan outlines the primary tools and channels used for communication within the project, including the ECHOES Teams group and various mailing lists. The plan details the procedures for accessing these platforms, managing communications, and ensuring that all relevant information is shared efficiently. Furthermore, it addresses the rhythm of communication, the responsibilities of various team members, and the proper documentation and storage of project materials. By adhering to these guidelines, the project team will foster transparent and organized communication, supporting the overall goals of ECHOES.

The main channels for general communication are the ECHOES group on Teams and the mailing lists. To first access the ECHOES Teams group, the Project Manager needs to add the new participant's email on the platform. Once the email is registered, the person will receive a link to enter the group. Due to the internal authorization settings of the institution hosting the ECHOES group in Teams, some

institutional emails do not have standard access. In this case, an alternative email address is required to obtain access to the group, its channels and documents.

The ECHOES Teams group is divided into 12 channels: one general channel and 11 Work Packages channels. The general channel is the main communication channel of the Coordination Team. The folders contain the agenda and presentation from ECHOES events; official documents such as the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement; reports including the final version of Deliverables and Milestones, the list and calendar of Deliverables and Milestones, and the internal progress reports from WP leaders and partners; and document related to internal consultations.

The WP channels are the main communication channel of the WP Leaders. The draft version of Deliverables, the minutes, agenda and attendees list of all the meetings and extra documents related to the work developed on tasks and sub-tasks are available in the folders.

Messages posted via Teams must also be shared on the corresponding mailing list. The following table contains all ECHOES mailing lists.

Name	Address
General ECHOES list All the members	echoes@groupe.renater.fr
General Assembly Representatives of partners	echoes_general_assembly@groupe.renater.fr
Steering Committee	echoes_sc@groupe.renater.fr
Executive Board	echoes_executive_board@groupe.renater.fr
WP 02	echoes.wp02@groupe.renater.fr
WP 03	echoes.wp03@groupe.renater.fr
WP 04	echoes.wp04@groupe.renater.fr
WP 05	echoes.wp05@groupe.renater.fr
WP 06	echoes.wp06@groupe.renater.fr
WP 07	echoes.wp07@groupe.renater.fr
WP 08	echoes.wp08@groupe.renater.fr
WP 09	echoes.wp09@groupe.renater.fr
WP 10	echoes.wp10@groupe.renater.fr
WP 11	echoes.wp11@groupe.renater.fr
Scientific Committee	echoes_scientific_committee@groupe.renater.fr
Policy Advisory Board	echoes_policy_advisory_board@groupe.renater.fr
Technical Assessment Committee	echoes_technical_assessment_committee@services.cnrs.fr
Stakeholders Council	echoes_stakeholders_council@services.cnrs.fr
ECHOES Diffusion Institutions interested in the project	echoes.diffusion@services.cnrs.fr
ECHOES integration Task Force	echoesintegrationtaskforce@groupe.renater.fr

Table 3: ECHOES' mailing list

All the lists are managed by the Coordination Team on the platform Renater. In addition, the WP leaders have access and rights to manage their lists on Renater by adding or removing contact addresses and to moderate messages sent by members.

A contact master list is available on Teams in the “General” channel folder, and it is accessible to all partners. It is divided into contact lists by WP. Partners are required to add or modify information about their team. The lists on Renater are synchronized by the coordination team and the WP leaders in accordance with this master list.

Rhythm of communication

The Project Manager will send reminders to the responsible for a Deliverable and Milestone one month and 15 days before the deadline.

For the internal progress reports, the same deadline is established. The reminders will be sent to the Work Package leaders and the designated representatives of Beneficiaries (list available in Annex 6 of the Consortium Agreement).

It is the Coordination Team’s responsibility to communicate to all partners when a Deliverable is uploaded on the EU Fundings & Tenders Portal or if it is delayed.

Communication with the European Commission is an exclusive responsibility of the Coordinator.

Document Control and Archiving

Gathering documents in one place with a clear allocation and denomination will facilitate democratic access for all members of this consortium. All the working and final documents will be available on the ECHOES Teams group and stored in the consortium’s shared repository, the SharePoint, which is accessible through Teams. This ensures traceability and compliance with Horizon Europe documentation standards.

If an alternative platform is being used for the work in progress, the WP leader must register in the Teams group which platform it is and for which task and sub-task it is being used.

The documents should be in English, shared in Word format when it is a draft version and in PDF as a final version.

The WP 2 channel - in the folder “Communication material” - has relevant template documents: Deliverables, presentations, agenda, minutes and list of attendees. The templates for the Internal progress report are available on Teams > General > Reporting > Internal Progress report folder. For the Beneficiaries, one standard template is available; and for the WP leaders were provided individual templates each trimester.

All documents uploaded onto the shared space must follow the following naming convention:

- YYMMDD_ECHOES_title_of_the_document;
- YYMMDD_ECHOES_WPXX_title_of_the_document;
- YYMMDD_ECHOES_[BOARD_ACRONYM]_Title_of_the_document

Working documents and draft versions are excluded from this naming convention.

Additionally, all the final documents are being stored in the University of Tours server by the Coordination Team.

1.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)

Progress Indicators at WP-Level will be monitored using predefined Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) specified in Annex 1 of the Grant Agreement. These KPIs will track the progress of deliverables and milestones for each WP.

This table outlines the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) associated with the specific objectives (SOs) of the project. Each KPI is designed to measure the progress and success of key deliverables under the corresponding objectives, with defined targets for completion. These indicators will help track the project's achievements and ensure that all milestones are met within the designated timeframes.

Additional KPIs for the ECCCH will be established by WP3, WP4, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP9, and WP11 under the responsibility of CYU. They are expected by Month 20 (January 2026).

No	KPI	Description	Target
SO1: Develop Open-Source Infrastructure			
1	KPI 1.1 Data Quality and Monitoring	The Data Management Plan (DMP) is published and implemented correctly by all partners.	DMP published by Month 6; annual compliance monitored.
2	KPI 1.2 Single Entry Point (SEP)	The SEP is functional and adopted by cultural heritage communities.	Annual increase in access after launch.
3	KPI 1.3 Heritage Digital Twin (HDT) Availability	Number of HDTs accessible through the platform.	>5,000 HDTs available by Month 60.
4	KPI 1.4 HDT Quality	Number of HDTs processed by tools on the platform.	>2,000 HDTs processed by Month 60.
5	KPI 1.5 Vertical Applications (VAs) Availability	Number of VAs available online for stakeholders.	Accessible VAs by Month 48.
6	KPI 1.6 Software Tools	Number of interoperable software tools accessible via the platform.	Target: >20 tools available by Month 48.
7	KPI 1.7 Cloud Performance Monitoring	Operational monitoring tools for cloud components.	Target: Fully functional tools by Month 48.
SO2: Establish a Sustainable Legal Entity			
8	KPI 2.1 Founding Members	Number of founding members for the legal entity	>20 members.

9	KPI 2.2 Geographical Balance	Representation of founding members from diverse regions.	Members from >10 countries.
10	KPI 2.3 Community Engagement	Number of umbrella organizations involved.	>15 umbrella organizations.
11	KPI 2.4 Financial Viability	Financial contributions for long-term sustainability secured.	Sustainable budget by Month 60.
SO3: Build a Community of Stakeholders			
12	KPI 3.1 Inclusion of Pan-European Stakeholders	Number of engaged institutions and individuals.	>500 stakeholders.
13	KPI 3.2 ECCCH Dissemination Strategy	Number of visits to the project website and campaign reach.	>60,000 visits annually.
14	KPI 3.3 Training and Capacity Building	Number of training sessions and participants.	>10 sessions with >200 participants.
15	KPI 3.4 Cascading Grants	Diversity of cultural heritage stakeholders receiving funding.	At least 45 projects funded.
SO4: Integrate Results of Past and Current Initiatives			
16	KPI 4.1 Inventory and Gap Analysis	Number of initiatives mapped and integrated.	>50 initiatives.
17	KPI 4.2 Synergy Creation	Number of collaborative projects launched through integration.	>10 joint projects.

18	KPI 4.3 Coordination and Networking	Engagement with ECCCH-funded projects and initiatives.	90% participation in general meetings.
SO5: Foster Innovative Knowledge Co-Creation			
19	KPI 5.1 Multidisciplinary Collaboration	Number of collaborative scientific publications and outputs.	>50 peer-reviewed articles.
20	KPI 5.2 Data Reuse and Enrichment	Increase in the reuse and enrichment of data.	Measured through platform analytics and user feedback.
21	KPI 5.3 Inclusivity	Number of projects addressing diversity and socio-cultural challenges.	>10 community-based projects.
22	KPI 5.4 Metadata Enhancement	Improvement in metadata quality and accessibility.	Increased access and reuse by stakeholders.

Table 4: KPIs description and targets

2. Risk Management Strategy

2.1 Risk Identification and Mitigation Plan

The ECHOES project operates within a complex framework involving numerous stakeholders, diverse disciplines, and cutting-edge technologies. This section identifies the primary risks that could impact project execution, categorizing them into scientific, technical, financial, regulatory, and operational domains.

No.	Description	Risk	Mitigation
1	Managing a large consortium/ Delays in performing activities	Coordinating 26 beneficiaries and affiliated entities from multiple countries could lead to inefficiencies, miscommunication, or delays in achieving milestones and deliverables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Establish a robust governance structure, as detailed in the Grant Agreement (Article 7). b. Schedule bi-monthly consortium meetings to track progress, address issues, and facilitate communication. c. Assign specific roles and responsibilities to WP leaders to ensure timely execution of tasks. d. Monitor deliverables through regular updates in the EU Funding & Tenders Portal.
2	Key personnel becoming unavailable	The loss of key personnel could disrupt project progress, particularly in leadership or technical roles.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Maintain a succession plan with backups identified for critical roles. b. Encourage cross-training within teams to ensure continuity. c. Include personnel availability updates in quarterly progress reports.
3	Actual costs exceed estimated costs	Financial overruns could jeopardize the ability to deliver	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Implement strict budget monitoring, with regular financial reporting as per Article 21.

		within the allocated €23,970,598 budget.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Allow reallocations between work packages only under justified circumstances and with prior approval (Article 5.5). c. Conduct semi-annual budget reviews to identify and address overspending early. d. Include a progress report on person-months of work compared to the allocated efforts in the quarterly progress reports.
4	Collaboration potential of ECHOES not fully exploited	Stakeholder engagement may fall short, limiting the project's ability to integrate fragmented communities in cultural heritage.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Develop a targeted communication and dissemination strategy (Article 17), including workshops, training, and stakeholder forums. b. Allocate resources for active outreach to underrepresented communities and smaller organizations. c. Regularly evaluate engagement metrics, such as participation rates and feedback.
5	Lack of collaboration with the projects funded under the ECCCH-related calls	Limited interaction with other funded projects could hinder the creation of a unified digital environment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Organize joint meetings and knowledge-sharing sessions with other Horizon Europe projects under the ECCCH-related calls. b. Establish a liaison officer role to coordinate activities with other consortia. c. Include collaboration updates in periodic technical reports.
6	Unsatisfactory results of the projects awarded through the Cascading Grants Programme	Cascading grants may result in underwhelming outcomes, affecting the overall quality of ECHOES outputs.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Design a rigorous evaluation and monitoring framework for cascading grant projects, with clear criteria and milestones. b. Provide technical and administrative support to funded projects to maximize their chances of success. c. Retain a portion of the budget as a contingency for addressing gaps.
7	Conceptual model of HDT not defined in time	Delays in defining the HeritageDigital Twin (HDT) model could impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Prioritize this task in the project timeline, with a defined milestone by Month 12 (Annex 1).

		subsequent development phases.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> b. Engage experts and allocate dedicated resources for conceptual development early in the project. c. Conduct interim reviews to ensure progress is on track.
8	Data aggregation routines not able to handle data sources relevant for HDT	Technical challenges in aggregating diverse datasets could compromise the effectiveness of the HDT model.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Use interactive testing during development to identify and address issues early. b. Collaborate with partners specializing in data aggregation to integrate advanced tools and methodologies. c. Schedule a comprehensive technical review of data routines by Month 18.
9	Applications delivered by the ECCCH are not fit for purpose	Tools and applications developed may not meet user requirements, reducing adoption and impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Conduct user needs assessments during the first six months of the project. b. Involve end-users in iterative testing phases to gather feedback and ensure alignment with needs from M25 to M48. c. Schedule a beta release of ECCCH applications by Month 36, followed by refinements based on feedback.
10	Infrastructure provided by WP6 cannot be used in the identified scenarios	The infrastructure developed in WP6 may not adequately support the scenarios identified during the planning phase, limiting the ECCCH's functionality.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Conduct scenario validation workshops during the design phase (by Month 12) to test infrastructure compatibility. b. Include contingency plans in WP6 for infrastructure adjustments, ensuring adaptability to unforeseen needs. c. Perform iterative testing with pilot users before full deployment (by Month 36).
11	The Knowledge Base and its tools do not satisfy community requirements	The Knowledge Base may not address the practical needs of heritage professionals, reducing adoption and impact.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Organize user engagement sessions early in the project to collect requirements (by Month 6) and integrate feedback into the design process. b. Establish an advisory panel of key stakeholders to review and validate tools during their development.

			c. Schedule iterative testing phases (by Months 18, 30, and 48) to refine tools based on community feedback.
12	Data loss/corruption (due to equipment failure, procedural failure, etc.), data privacy	Loss or corruption of critical data could undermine project progress and stakeholder trust, while data privacy breaches may violate EU standards.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Implement robust data management protocols aligned with Horizon Europe's requirements for data protection (Article 15). b. Perform regular backups with off-site storage to minimize data loss risks. c. Conduct security audits quarterly to identify and address vulnerabilities.
13	Innovation: Delays in the VAs deployment	Delays in Virtual Agents (VAs) deployment may hinder the project's ability to meet its milestones and deliverables.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Set a clear timeline for VAs development with intermediate checkpoints (by Months 12, 24, and 36). b. Allocate dedicated resources and teams to focus on VAs deployment. c. Include a risk buffer in the timeline to accommodate unforeseen challenges.
14	Tools created do not function as planned or do not satisfy requirements	The tools developed may fail to meet performance or usability expectations, reducing their effectiveness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Define clear success metrics for each tool during the design phase and validate them through regular testing. b. Engage users in the co-creation process to ensure tools align with practical needs. c. Allocate resources for bug fixes and performance optimization during the final project phase (Months 48-60).
15	The cloud services fail to achieve expected results	The ECCCH cloud services may not provide the expected functionalities or scale required by the community.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Collaborate with experienced cloud infrastructure providers to ensure scalability and reliability. b. Include stress testing and performance optimization as part of WP6 deliverables (by Month 30). c. Monitor cloud services using real-time analytics to identify and address issues promptly.

16	Sustainability: The stakeholder's engagement in the governance-building process is low or unstable	Limited or inconsistent engagement from stakeholders could compromise the establishment of a sustainable governance model for ECCCH.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Create a targeted communication plan to engage stakeholders early and maintain their interest throughout the project. b. Organize biannual stakeholder forums to gather input and keep stakeholders informed of progress. c. Leverage the project's advisory board to champion the governance-building process and advocate for its importance.
17	Feasibility of the business plan after the end of the project	The business plan for ECCCH may lack sufficient feasibility or funding pathways, jeopardizing sustainability post-project.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> a. Conduct a feasibility study by Month 48 to assess potential funding sources and revenue streams. b. Include private and public stakeholders in the development of the business plan to ensure alignment with their priorities. c. Explore partnerships with external organizations to secure long-term financial support.

Table 5: Risk identification and mitigation plan

2.2 Risk Monitoring and Reporting

In order to ensure that risks are continuously monitored and addressed, the ECHOES consortium will implement a structured process for tracking, evaluating, and mitigating risks throughout the project lifecycle.

Regarding reporting mechanisms, WP leaders will submit quarterly risk updates to the project manager, including any new risks, updates on mitigation actions, and issues requiring consortium-level intervention.

A summary of risk management activities will be included in the periodic technical and financial reports submitted to the European Commission, following Article 21 of the Grant Agreement.

As part of the escalation protocol, high-impact risks requiring immediate action will be escalated to the project Steering Committee (SC) for strategic decision-making. The SC will provide guidance on resource reallocation, timeline adjustments and other corrective actions.

By combining regular updates and real-time monitoring, the ECHOES consortium ensures a proactive approach to risk management and minimizing its impact on the project's objectives.

2.3 Risk Owner Assignment

To ensure accountability in risk management, each identified risk will be assigned a specific risk owner responsible for its monitoring, mitigation, and reporting.

No	Role	Description
1	WP Leaders as Primary Risk Owners	Each WP leader will serve as the primary risk owner for risks specific to their work package. They will oversee the identification and mitigation of risks within their scope and provide regular updates to the project manager.
2	Project Manager	The project manager will act as the central risk coordinator, consolidating updates from WP leaders, maintaining the risk register, and ensuring that mitigation measures are implemented across the consortium. For consortium-wide risks, such as delays in deliverables or stakeholder engagement issues, the project manager will collaborate with the scientific coordinator and escalate as needed to the PSC.
3	Scientific Coordinator	The scientific coordinator will be responsible for overseeing high-level scientific risks, such as unsatisfactory results from the Knowledge Base or delays in the definition of the HDT model.
4	Specialized Risk Ownership	Data Privacy and Security Risks (e.g., data loss or corruption): Assigned to the WP6 leader, who will work with external IT consultants to ensure compliance with EU data protection standards (Article 15 of the Grant Agreement). Sustainability Risks (e.g., stakeholder engagement and business plan feasibility): Assigned to the WP7 leader, responsible for governance-building and post-project sustainability.
5	Consortium-Level Support	For cross-cutting risks, such as those related to collaboration across WPs or with external stakeholders, the Project Steering Committee will provide oversight and guidance to ensure alignment and effective resolution.

Table 6: Risk owner and their responsibilities

By clearly assigning responsibilities, the consortium ensures that risks are managed efficiently and transparently, with all partners contributing to the project's overall success.

Conclusion

The ECHOES Quality and Risk Management Plan (QRMP) establishes a comprehensive framework to ensure the successful delivery of the project's objectives while maintaining the highest standards of quality and effectively managing potential risks. By defining clear processes for quality assurance, risk identification, and mitigation, this document serves as a roadmap for ensuring the project's compliance with Horizon Europe requirements and the expectations of its diverse stakeholders.

The QRMP is designed to be a living document, evolving alongside the project to adapt to new challenges and opportunities. Regular monitoring and evaluation will ensure that all work packages, deliverables, and milestones are achieved within the defined scope, timeframes, and budget. Key tools, such as progress indicators, reporting mechanisms, and iterative reviews, will support the project consortium in maintaining transparency, accountability, and a collaborative spirit throughout the project lifecycle.

Moreover, the strong emphasis on stakeholder engagement, sustainability, and inclusivity reflects the project's commitment to creating a long-lasting impact on the cultural heritage community. The consortium will continue to foster collaboration, leverage innovative technologies, and uphold ethical standards to deliver the European Collaborative Cloud for Cultural Heritage (ECCCH) as a transformative platform that aligns with the principles of Open Science and Open Access.

Through diligent adherence to the strategies outlined in this QRMP, the ECHOES consortium reaffirms its dedication to achieving excellence and ensuring the project's success for the benefit of heritage professionals, researchers, and society at large.